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Development of a 5 – Layer Multipurpose Sieving Machine

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the design and development of a multi-layered sieving machine for efficient and effective particle separation. The machine is designed to sieve granular materials such as sand, gravel, and agricultural products such as cassava flour (gari) to obtain the desired grain sizes. The sieving machine consists of five layers of sieves with mesh sizes of 1.5 mm, 2 mm, 3 mm, 4 mm, and 5 mm. It is powered by an electric motor connected to a pulley and belt system, which drives the sieves in a reciprocating motion. The machine's performance was evaluated through sieving tests, demonstrating its ability to efficiently separate particles based on their sizes. Results indicated a sieving an average efficiency of 74.78 % thus highlighting the machine's effectiveness in particle separation. The machine is capable of sieving a variety of materials quickly and efficiently, making it suitable for industrial, agricultural, and domestic applications.

Keywords: Multipurpose, Sieving machine, Agricultural materials, Construction Materials, Sand separation

1. INTRODUCTION

In various industries, the process of separating particles or materials of different sizes is a crucial operation. The sieving process is a fundamental method utilized in many sectors such as agriculture, mining, pharmaceuticals, and construction. The evolution of sieving technology has been remarkable, transforming the way particles are separated by size across various industries. From ancient sieves made of woven reeds to modern automated machines, sieving has evolved to be more efficient, precise, and adaptable. Ancient civilizations used simple sieves made from materials like woven reeds or fabrics. The Industrial Revolution introduced mechanical sieving machines powered by water wheels or steam engines, significantly boosting productivity in industries such as mining and agriculture. In the 20th century, vibrating sieves and specialized equipment emerged, improving efficiency and precision. Today, modern sieving technologies like vibrating sieves and centrifugal sifters cater to specific industries, enabling high-quality product separation with minimal waste. Orojinmi developed a laterite sieve and conducted a performance evaluation, resulting in an efficiency of 76 % and an output capacity of 69.12 kg/h [1]. The study recommended improvements to enhance efficiency, capacity, and reduce the labor-

intensive aspects of the sieving operation. A multi-purpose wet food sieving machine was developed by Fayose that includes of a mixing compartment, a hopper, a sieving compartment that uses a crank and spring arrangement with collecting trays and outlets [2]. The volumetric flow rate was $0.0206 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$ and the machine capacity was 22.45 kg/h . The study was carried out at three concentration levels of 12.2 %, 14.44 %, and 22.77 %. The results obtained showed that the machine's performance coefficients and sieving capacity increased with decreasing concentration. The highest performance coefficient of 98 % was observed for sieving maize, while the sieving capacity of 16.90 g/sm^2 was obtained when the machine was used to sieve cassava. Samaila et al. developed and evaluated a motorized cassava sieving machine that employed a 3.41 kW petrol engine, and has an overall dimensions of $1117 \text{ mm} \times 1045 \text{ mm} \times 500 \text{ mm}$ [3]. The sifting unit consisted of a $980 \text{ mm} \times 25 \text{ mm}$ diameter shaft with 16 mm alternately arranged rods and bristles rubbing brushes for pulverization. In addition, spikes were incorporated between the first two brushes to aid in breaking cassava mash lumps. The sieve is concave shaped, made of 1.5 mm thick stainless-steel measuring 800 mm by 400 mm and perforated with 2 mm diameter holes. A rubber seal was placed between the upper concave cover and the sieve to prevent cassava mash from leaking. The sieve demonstrated a sifting efficiency of 90 % at a sifting speed of 450 rpm , with an output capacity of 132.78 kg/h at a moisture content of 40 %. The particle sizes of the sifted mash ranged from 0.378 mm to 0.38 mm , and the fineness module was 1.91. Kudabo et al. developed a motorized laterite sieving machine powered by an electric motor, with dimensions of $915 \text{ mm} \times 455 \text{ mm} \times 630 \text{ mm}$ [4]. The machine demonstrated a high efficiency of 93.3% at 26% moisture content, operating at a sieving speed of 410 rpm and achieving an output capacity of 135 kg/h . This development is significant for the efficient processing of laterite, a commonly used material in construction and road building. The compact size and reported performance characteristics of the machine make it a promising addition to laterite processing operations, with the potential to improve overall productivity and cost-effectiveness in relevant industries. Ogunwole designed, constructed, and tested a dry sand sieving machine, which is crucial for various construction and industrial applications [5]. The machine is intended to sieve uniformly graded sand with a coefficient of uniformity of 1.11, but cannot sieve larger particles such as gravel. The slip calculated for the machine is 36 %, which enabled the proper configuration of the V – belt. The theoretical efficiency of the machine is calculated to be 97 %. The research provides valuable insights into the design and construction of a dry sand sieving machine, which is important for various construction and industrial applications. Jackson and Oladipo conducted a study at the National Centre for Agricultural Mechanization (NCAM) to develop and evaluate a motorized laterite sieve [6]. The research aimed to determine the effects of operating speed on the machine's sieving efficiency. The operating speed was varied four times during the study, at 450, 500, 600, and 650 rpms . The machine sieved 15 kg of laterite sample at each speed, and the time taken for the sieving operations was recorded. The study revealed that the sieving efficiency was 86.5% at an operating speed of 650 rpm , while the lowest efficiency of 75.5 % was observed at 450 rpm . Additionally, the machine achieved an output of 200 kg/h . Mohammed et al. developed a pedal-driven pulverizing and sieving machine for dewatered grated cassava to mechanize the traditional method of pulverizing and sieving cassava lump in gari production [7]. The machine was designed to be driven like a bicycle and rotates the system. It accepts cassava lumps through the hopper into the pulverizer. The pulverizer rotates at a speed higher than that of the lump, breaking it into smaller particles. The performance of the machine increases with an increase in the amount of cassava lump inserted, with efficiency improving from 80 % and 83 % to 86 % and 85 % for the TMS 82/00058 and TMS 82/00661 varieties, respectively. Kahandage et al developed a reciprocating type sawdust sieving machine to address the need for finely sieved sawdust in Sri Lanka's wood cutting industry [8]. Sawdust is a valuable resource used as a primary substrate in various applications, including mushroom production. While traditional sieving methods involve labor-intensive processes with limited efficiency, this new machine offers a solution for higher yields in mushroom cultivation. The machine can sieve 212 kg of sawdust per hour with an efficiency rate of 84 %, reducing labor requirements and operating costs for mushroom growers. Aldo [9] designed and fabricated an inclinable multi-layer trommel sand sieving machine to address issues in sieve machines integrated with flat screens. The machine was made up of concentrically arranged trommels with different mesh sizes for each layer and an inclination mechanism

controlled by a power screw ranging from 0° to 16.2° . The study conducted tests to determine the optimum inclination and maximum feed rate capacity of the machine for dry and wet feed. The results showed a dry feed rate of 28.55 kg/min with 96.5 % screening efficiency and a wet feed rate of 21.2 kg/min with 98 % screening efficiency. Vilas et al. [10] developed a multi-stage sand separator and filter system for efficient sand separation in construction and manufacturing processes. The conventional methods were found to be time-consuming and labor-intensive, leading to the design of this innovative machine. The machine is designed to separate sand into different sizes for various construction processes, such as column/beam construction, plaster, and flooring. The system is equipped with three different sizes of filters and three different compartments to separate sand efficiently. The motor drives the slider crank mechanism, which in turn moves the tray to vibrate and act as a separator with the help of a DC motor. The machine aims to reduce costs, increase productivity, and produce less waste, benefiting industrial people and farmers worldwide. Ramarao et al [11] developed a fully automated sand filtering and separator system designed to filter sand poured onto it. The system features a motorized shaft mounted horizontally using mounts and connected to a filter frame with mesh below and an enclosing frame on the sides. A rod connects the shaft to the filter frame to achieve optimal horizontal motion, while a frame holds the filter frame in place and ensures proper horizontal motion. The motor controller circuit allows the system to operate the sand filter motion as needed for sand filtering. This machine reduces the cost and complexity of sand filtering and separation, making it suitable for laboratory and small construction site use. Ikechukwu and Agu [12] designed and developed a motorized cassava mash sieving machine that comprises a 3hp electric motor, pulverization unit, sieving unit, collection unit, and fiber outlet. The machine breaks and sieves dewatered cassava mash, allowing the fiber to exit through the fiber outlet, thus reducing drudgery and time wastage. It also eliminates human contact with the cassava, unlike existing semi-mechanized and traditional sieving methods. Performance test analysis revealed that the developed machine achieved an average throughput of 174.46 kg/h at 25 % moisture content, significantly outperforming the manual/traditional process. Gajbhiye et al. [13] designed and fabricated an automatically driven sand sieving machine, aiming to reduce the time consumed during the process of preparing concrete. The authors emphasized the importance of sand sieving in construction, where sand is used at different stages, requiring proper screening for various construction needs. Traditionally, the sieving process is carried out manually using fixed screens or machines, which is time-consuming, laborious, and costly. The authors proposed an automatic sand sieving machine to address these challenges, with the process taking place automatically, reducing the time consumed during the whole process of preparing concrete. Baliram et al. [14] designed and fabricated a multi-layer sieving machine that is different from existing machines in the market. The machine is based on a new innovation that allows it to sieve materials into three different layers with the same effort and less time required. The machine operates on the principle of vibration generated by the rotation of cranks and connecting links. It is designed to generate three different types and sizes of sieve, with the largest sieve at the top position, medium at the middle, and the smallest at the bottom position. This design allows for the separation of all types of sieves at an inclined post. Mahure et al. [15] developed a conceptual model of a Multi-purpose Sieving Machine designed to improve efficiency and reduce costs in manufacturing. The machine can perform multiple operations simultaneously, including sawing and vibrating the tray to act as a divider. Key components include a motor to drive the main shaft, a slider-crank mechanism for sawing, and a table with a crank to move the tray. This machine offers benefits such as easy separation of objects by mesh size, reduced electricity costs, increased production rate, and reduced space requirements. Fabricated using components like a motor, crank and slider link mechanism, bearing, C.I. wheels, and sieving box, the Multi-purpose Sieving Machine provides a cost-effective solution for industries such as food processing, mining, and pharmaceuticals. Ovat et al. [16] developed a commercial-scaled motorized vibratory gari sieving machine featuring a 3-phase motor with one horsepower operating at 1500 rpm . This machine offers several advantages over traditional sieving methods, including increased output per time, improved hygiene, higher gari quality, and reduced processing time. Performance evaluation showed an efficiency of about 96 %, surpassing existing machines with efficiencies ranging from 50 % and above. The study suggests that the motorized vibratory gari sieving machine is a practical solution for

enhancing gari production and processing, particularly in Nigeria and similar food processing contexts. Nwankwojike et al. [17] integrated a rotary vacuum drum filter into a milling and sieving machine for continuous slurry starch production. The machine operates with an average throughput of 70.44 kg/h and 98.48 % extraction efficiency, reducing moisture content to 31.52 % in the processed slurry starch cake. This innovation saves over 5.39 hours and reduces water consumption by recycling drained water. It also improves hygiene and reduces drudgery by eliminating human contact during loading/discharging. Adejugbe et al. [18] developed a laterite sieving machine to improve the efficiency of sieving laterite sand for construction, reducing manual labor. The machine, powered by a 2.43 kW diesel engine, operates at 440 rpm with a sieving capacity of 300 kg/h. It features a crank and slider mechanism, including a prime mover, hopper, driving/driven pulley, belt guard, sieving unit, and machine frame fabricated using welding and machining. Testing with dry laterite samples showed sieving efficiency ranging from 92 % to 97 %, demonstrating high efficiency, reliability, and durability. Performance evaluation yielded a sieving efficiency of 96 %. Kiprotich et al. [19]. Designed a sand screening machine and investigated the effect of moisture and sieve sizes on screening time. The machine was semi-automatic and driven by a motor, and experiments were conducted to determine the fine sand produced at different moisture levels and time consumed. The machine was designed with a motor, sieve, shaft, steel hollow tubes, flat steel bars, sheet metal plates, hinges, eccentric sheaves, and angle bars. The study found that screening raw sand of 10 kg using a semi-automatic machine with a sieve of 3 mm x 3 mm and densities ranging from 1442 kg/m³ to 2082 kg/m³ produced 8.1 kg to 2.8 kg of sand, respectively, with sieving times ranging from 24 s to 32 s. The designed machine displayed a labor reduction cost of 66 %, leading to savings of Ksh. 39,600 per month. The study recommends the use of low-density sand and adoption of semi-automatic screening machine technologies in the construction industry to achieve Kenya's affordable housing program. Ajayi and Oyeniyi [20] developed a mechanical sieving machine with an automatic vibrator for efficiently sieving granulated materials like sand. Manual sieving is time-consuming, while mechanical sieving is faster and requires only operator oversight. The machine uses an electric motor connected to a reciprocating sieve screen through a connecting rod. It offers an overview of its working principle, design, and operation, highlighting its potential to enhance efficiency in various industrial operations. This paper presents the design and development of a multipurpose 5 - layer sieving machine that aims to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of particle separation.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials used

Components used in fabricating the sieving machine includes the following:

1. **Electric Motor:** The electric motor embedded within the sieving machine stands as the driving force behind its operation, converting electrical energy into mechanical motion to initiate the sieving process. 0.74 hp electric motor was used based on the design calculation requirement
2. **Belts and Pulley:** Belts and pulleys are fundamental components within the sieving machine, crucial for the transmission of rotational energy from the electric motor to the sieving mechanism. The Belt and pulleys were used in connecting the power from the electric motor to be transmitted to the sieves.
3. **Slider crank arrangement (connecting rod):** The slider crank mechanism is important in the sieving machine, converting the electric motor's rotational motion into the necessary reciprocating or oscillating motion for sieving. It comprises three key components: the crank, connecting rod, and slider, each fulfilling a specific role in motion conversion.
4. **Shaft and bearing:** The shaft and bearings play vital roles in the sieving machine, ensuring its structural stability and operational efficiency. The shaft transmits rotational energy from the electric motor to the machine's moving parts.
5. **Sieves/mesh:** The sieves, also known as mesh, are critical components of sieving machines, serving as the barriers through which particles are sorted based on size. Five sieves of different screen sizes (5 mm, 4 mm, 3.5 mm, 2 mm and 1mm) were used.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Working principle

The five-layer sieving machine, with sieve sizes of 5 mm, 4 mm, 3.5 mm, 2 mm, and 1 mm, operates by using an electric motor to drive a system of belts and pulleys, along with a slider crank arrangement, to achieve precise particle separation. The motor's rotational force is transmitted through the belts and pulleys, creating a motion that is then converted into a back-and-forth movement by the slider crank arrangement. This reciprocating motion causes the sieve decks to vibrate, allowing smaller particles to pass through the mesh apertures while larger particles remain on top, resulting in effective particle separation based on size.

2.3 Design Calculation

The design calculations in this section had been done in [20] according to Adhapure et al. [21] but will be repeated here.

2.3.1 Power calculation:

$$\text{Power} = \text{Force} \times \text{velocity}$$

$$\text{Force} = \text{Weight} = mg$$

where

$$m = \text{mass of sand} = 3 \text{ kg (for this purpose only)}$$

$$g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 \text{ (acceleration due to gravity)}$$

$$\text{Power} = \text{Force} \times \text{Velocity}$$

$$= m \times g \times v$$

If 25 % margin of safety is proposed then

$$\text{Power required} = \text{Force} \times \text{Velocity},$$

Where

$$v = r\omega$$

$$r = \text{radius of the pulley} = 1.33 \times mgv$$

$$\omega = \text{angular velocity of the pulley}$$

$$v = 0.025 \text{ m} \times 300 \text{ m} = 7.5 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Power, } P = 1.33 \times 3 \times 9.81 \times 7.5 \text{ W}$$

$$= 293.56 \text{ W}$$

So, it is safe to use ½ hp electric motor because it is more than 1/3 hp (248.4 W)

2.3.2 Torque Calculation:

Torque is calculated from the Power generated by the motor to operate the machine,

$$\text{Diameter of pulley} = 0.20 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Number of revolution (N)} = 1500 \text{ rpm}$$

$$\text{Power of the electric motor} = \frac{1}{2} \text{ hp} = 375 \text{ W}$$

$$\text{Force (F)} = m \times r \times \omega^2$$

$$\text{Where } m \text{ is the total mass of the rotation chamber} = 15 \text{ kg, } \omega = 157.1 \text{ rad/s}$$

$$\text{Torque (given by motor)} = \text{power}/\omega = 375/157.1 = 2.387 \text{ Nm}$$

2.3.3 RPM:

Motor pulley diameter (outer) = 0.10 m

Machine pulley diameter (outer) = 0.50 m

Speed ratio = 10/50 = 0.20

For a machine with 1,500 rpm, the speed of the rotating arm = 1,500 × 0.20 = 300 rpm

2.3.4 Belt and Pulley design

i) Pulley design

The diameter of the pulley of the shaft was calculated to be 320 mm using the expression given in [22]

$$N_1 d_1 = N_2 d_2 \quad (1)$$

where $N_1 = 1410 \text{ rpm}$

$$d_1 = 80 \text{ mm}$$

$$d_2 = 260 \text{ mm}$$

$$\begin{aligned} N_2 &= \frac{1410 \times 80}{260} \\ &= 434 \text{ rpm} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

ii) Belt design

The belt speed, v (m/s) and its total belt length, (m), were calculated using the expression given in [21]

$$v = \frac{\pi d N}{60} \quad (3)$$

where,

v = Velocity of the belt,

N = Revolution of the motor,

d = Diameter of the motor pulley

$$v = \frac{\pi \times 1410 \times 0.08}{60} \quad (4)$$

$$v = 5.9 \text{ m/s}$$

iii) Belt length

For the best performance of the machine, the Centre distance, C, between the pulleys was determined to be $260 \text{ mm} = 0.26 \text{ m}$

The belt length can be determined using (5) [21].

$$L = \frac{\pi}{2}(d_1 + d_2) + 2C + \frac{1}{4C}(d_1 + d_2)^2 \quad (5)$$

where

Diameter of small pulley, $d_1 = 80 \text{ mm} = 0.08 \text{ m}$

Diameter of large pulley, $d_2 = 260 \text{ mm} = 0.26 \text{ m}$

$$\therefore L = \frac{\pi}{2}(0.08 + 0.26) + 2 \times 0.26 + \frac{1}{(4 \times 0.26)}(0.08 + 0.26)^2 \quad (6)$$

$$L = 1.165 \text{ m}$$

iv) Determination of Belt tension

The tension on the belt was determined using equations as shown below for both the driver pulley and the driven pulley.

Torque transmitted by electric motor; it is given by:

$$T = \frac{P}{\omega} \quad (7)$$

Where

P = Power transmitted by electric motor = $3/4 \text{ hp} = 551.82 \text{ W}$

ω = angular speed of the electric motor

$$\omega = \frac{2\pi N}{60} \quad (8)$$

N = Speed of rotation of the electric motor = 1410 rpm

$$\omega = \frac{2 \times 3.142 \times 1410}{60} = 147.7 \text{ rad/secs}$$

$$\text{Peripheral velocity, } v = \omega r \quad (9)$$

$$= 147.7 \times 0.04$$

$$= 5.91 \text{ ms}^{-1}$$

2.3.5 Torsional force in shaft

Maximum tensile stress of a mild steel = 525 MPa

Maximum shear stress of mild steel = 525/1.75
= 300 MPa

Diameter of shaft (D) = 20 mm = 0.02 m

$$\text{Torque transmitted by circular shaft} = \frac{\pi}{16} \times \tau \times D^3 \quad (8)$$

$$= \frac{\pi}{16} \times 300 \times (2)^3$$

$$= 471 \text{ Nm}$$

2.5 Experimental Setup

The model and the constructed 5-stage sand sieving machine is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 respectively. The main aim of this machine is to sieve/clean particles of particular sizes from impurities such as dirt and pebble stones for different purposes domestic, agricultural and industrial purposes. The sieving machine is made up of a main frame, electric motor, reciprocating connecting rod, 5-layers sieving mesh/screens, drive belt for power transmission, and collector. The purpose of the main frame is to support the whole body of the machine and provide a guide for the reciprocating movements of the sieve. There is no supporting wheel for the sieving machine to move to prevent unwanted movement during the operation of the machine. Five different sieve mesh/screens were used to sieve to obtain different grain sizes. The electric motor provides the power for the sieving machine. The power is transmitted through the pulley, the connecting belt, the shaft and the connecting rod to the mesh for sieving operation [20].

Figure 1a: Exploded drawing of the 5-stage sieving machine

Figure 1b: Assembly drawing of the 5-stage sieving machine

Figure 2a: The Side View of the 5-stage Sieving machine

Figure 2b: Front View of the 5-stage Sieving Machine

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Sieving Efficiency Analysis

For the purpose of evaluating the machine and determining the optimum working conditions for five-layer sieving machine, 2 kg and 3 kg of dried sand with sizes less than 5 mm were used for the first test and second testing respectively. The sand was fed into the first sieve with 5 mm screen sieve and the sand gets to the other sieves below it as the sieving chamber oscillates. This was repeated 5 times for accuracy and the average sand retained were tabulated in Table 1 and Table 2.

4.2 Results

Table 1: Sieve sizes and the quantity it retains when 2 kg of sand was used

Sieve Screen (mm)	Size	Mass Retained (g)	Retained Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
5		0	0.00	0.00
4		15	0.75	0.75
3.5		40	2.00	2.75
2		192	9.60	12.35
1		257	12.85	25.20
Collector		1496	74.80	100.00

Table 2: Sieve sizes and the quantity it retains when 3 kg of sand was used

Sieve Screen (mm)	Size	Mass Retained (g)	Retained Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
5		0	0.00	0.00
4		25	0.83	0.83
3.5		65	2.17	3.00
2		292	9.73	12.73
1		370	12.3	25.06
Collector		2258	75.07	100.00

4.3 DISCUSSIONS

The results of the sieving tests indicate the efficiency of the sieving machine in separating sand particles of different sizes. Table 1, in the first test, with a total mass of 2000 g (2 kg) of dried sand used, the machine achieved an average sieving efficiency of 74.80 %. This means that averagely, 74.80 % of the sand was successfully separated into different particle sizes, while the remaining 25.20 % were left behind on the screens. Considering the individual sieve sizes, it is evident that the majority of the sand particles were retained in the 1mm sieve, this indicates that a significant portion of the sand particles had a size close to or smaller than 1mm. The 2mm sieve also retained a substantial amount of sand.

Table 2 in the second test, with a total mass of 3000 g (3 kg) of dried sand used, the sieving machine achieved a slightly lower sieving efficiency of 75.07 %. This indicates that the machine was slightly more effective in separating the sand particles compared to the first test. However, the overall trend in particle distribution across the sieves was similar to the first test, with the 1 mm and 2 mm screen sieves retaining the most sand.

4. CONCLUSION

A 5-layer multipurpose sieving machine was constructed. The sieving machine demonstrated effective particle separation capabilities, with sieving efficiencies of 74.80 % and 75.07 % in the two tests conducted. The machine effectively separated dried sand particles into different sizes, with the 1 mm and 2 mm sieves retaining the most particles. These results indicate that the machine can be used successfully for separating particles based on size, with potential applications in industries requiring different particle sizing. The machine can sieve and separate 2 kg of sand and other grains in 2 mins.

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